

CAN THE PHILOSOPHY OF HUMAN-CENTEREDNESS BECOME A UNIFYING IDEOLOGY OF UKRAINE'S DEVELOPMENT?

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Abstract

The entire system of public administration consists of elements – people in certain structures, the potential of which should be used in the direction of achieving the ultimate goals with their coordinated interaction.

In Ukraine, it has already become common to say that our state is being destroyed by corruption. At the same time, this is already common not only inside the country, but also had come out. And even martial law does not help the fight against corruption invincibility, because it has deep roots in our country. How exactly can the problem of conscious development of post-war Ukraine be solved, eliminating forever its “blind style” movement towards progress?

In this article, authors propose a way to solve these problems with the help of a system complex of four blocks, which is called “The New Human-Centered Management Course”.

Keywords: public administration, human-centeredness, civil society, quality of life of citizens, The New Human-Centered Management Course (NHMC).

Introduction. Is our "system of public administration" similar to the real system as a holistic phenomenon, all structures of which are united by a single ultimate goal with well-established interaction from the bottom to the highest level in order to achieve this ultimate goal? We have always had slogans, but we have never had a real ultimate goal, the achievement of which would be recorded in clearly defined results, for which the authorities would be responsible.

We also have the concept of "ruling elite", which in its essence did not consist of the best (which suggests the very concept of "elite" as the chosen ones). In Ukraine, there have always been no "white" filters in line with "ability", and hopes for the objectivity of the electoral system were in vain, because it was quickly distorted with money and connections.

Presentation of the main material. The entire system of public administration consists of elements, people in certain structures, the potential of which should be used in the direction of achieving the ultimate goals with their coordinated interaction. Then corruption will not be able to demonstrate its invincibility.

The philosophy of human-centeredness is at the heart of democracy, the degree of development of which today becomes an indicator of belonging to modern civilization. The understanding of this fact even reached the Ukrainian authorities, when, under the fourth President, billboards were distributed throughout the country: "Ukraine for the people". That is, the authorities realized the attractiveness of joining the values of democracy in modern civilization, but everything was in vain. The people could no longer trust such a government, because the real corruption of its structures at all hierarchical levels significantly contradicted these slogans on billboards.

But how can the problem of conscious development of post-war Ukraine be solved, eliminating forever its “blind style” movement towards progress? Since Ukraine's “random” course led the young state into a deadlock, much attention should be paid to determining its own path to modern civilization. At the same time, adhering to democracy in the context of the implementation of the ideology of eco-human-centrism, that is, relying on the priority of the human factor in all spheres of organization of society, primarily political and economic. This will be the first general milestone that points to the right path of post-war Ukraine.

The second milestone of the conscious path to progress is associated with the definition of a specific orientation (without another slogan) of power structures to improve the quality of life of citizens. At the same time, in such a way that the authorities are interested in this, and people realize that this is real and will be implemented in practice.

The third milestone of the conscious movement is the technology of measuring the quality of life of citizens (QLC) in the form of respective indices, which at the same time become a digital assessment of the resulting activities of government structures (that had been repeatedly mentioned above). This innovation is of fundamental importance, because it determines Ukraine's own path to civilization. It was possible to implement it due to the understanding of the essence of the concept of "quality of life of citizens" through a person's internal perception of the level of satisfaction of his needs and application of the qualimetric digitization from fuzzy mathematics.

After that, another interesting milestone naturally appears, this is the transition to a culture of systemic management based on the final results of all power structures at all hierarchical levels.

One thing is important, that all innovative components of the Ukrainian path to progress start and are intended for the implementation of the ideology of human-centrism (eco-human-centrism).

In Ukraine, the saying that our state is being destroyed by corruption has already become commonplace. In general, Ukraine has a bitter experience of unsuccessful fight against corruption by legal methods, after the use of which prisons for corrupt officials remained practically empty. And not because of their execution, as they do in China with the organizers of corruption schemes, but because of their ransom, including from judges. And this despite the fact that from 1997 [1] to 2011. six (!) Presidential Decrees were issued, and in 2014 the Law of Ukraine "On the Principles of State Anti-Corruption Policy in Ukraine" was even adopted [2].

At one time, Singapore proved (building a society of social justice with a multilingual and multi-ethnic population) what it means to consciously move towards progress, relying on common sense and a certain strategy, where the main place was occupied by the slogan: "To restore order in your country".

To restore order means, first of all, to concentrate the actions of the authorities on the interests of citizens and to orient these actions to improve the lives of the country's residents. Since corruption is a big obstacle on this path, Singapore paid great attention to it from the very beginning. How was it done?

Six years before the declaration of independence, the chairman of the People's Action Party, Lee Kuan Yew, stated that "our goal is to create an honest administrative body, because we are already tired of the greed, corruption and licentiousness of many Asian leaders" [3, p. 175]. And from the first days of his activity in power in the conditions of independence, Lee Kuan Yew with like-minded people from the PAP took up the matter with their own. They began to create an atmosphere of intolerance to corruption in society and widely highlight the signs of corruption, then "established strict control over areas in which abuse of power had previously occurred and it was possible to enrich oneself at the expense of citizens; tools were developed to prevent the actions of such enrichment mechanisms" [3, p. 177]. The work of the Anti-Corruption Bureau was intensified, directing it against corrupt officials in the highest echelons of power. This also included the decision "to automatically transfer the salaries of ministers, judges, and senior officials, tied to the amount of income tax in the private sector" [3, p. 187].

At the end, a corruption prevention mechanism was created in Singapore, which placed it into the group of the least corrupt countries in the world [4]. Unfortunately, Ukraine in this ranking is in the group of the most corrupt countries with the most hardened corrupt officials having all-encompassing intertwined ties.

The fact is that if the QLC indicator is determined annually, then the dynamics of positive or negative (successful or unsuccessful, effective or ineffective) activities of the authorities for the corresponding period of time (year) is revealed. That is, the next year becomes, as it were, a controller of the previous one along the entire chain of public administration structures,

both horizontally and vertically. A characteristic feature of these chains is the dependence of each of the structures on the activities of others, primarily vertically.

For example, we are talking about meeting the needs in the living conditions in the house (in terms of electricity supply), or medical care, or environmental safety, etc. From the above-mentioned area, not everything depends on local authorities, here it is impossible to do without the actions of regional authorities and even authorities at the national level.

Since the integral indicators of the QLC in communities are indigenous information, they are distributed from the bottom up to the power structures in a digital way and become an assessment of the effectiveness of their resulting activities. This assessment is legally enshrined, thereby legally confirming the responsibility of the authorities for a happy life (after covering the index of self-realization in the sphere of personal life) of their people.

The main sign of the weakness of civil society in Ukraine is the presence of corruption, which resembles an impenetrable wall. In countries with developed civil society, it was possible to overcome this wall, bearing in mind that the general purpose of this society is to promote the free development and self-realization of a person, as well as to specifically limit the arbitrariness of power and direct the activities of its structures for the benefit of people. That is, civil society is inherently a lever (or a powerful technology) for the implementation of the ideology of human-centrism in modern civilization, which is not developed in countries with dictatorial regimes.

There are also other signs of the weakness of civil society in Ukraine, already on the part of the people themselves, who are not yet ready to live in such a society. This is confirmed by the research of a group of civil servants and a group of experimental psychologists [5; 6].

For example, a group of civil servants led by N. Dniprenko [5], based on the Constitution of Ukraine, identified 9 positions according to which citizens have the right to participate in the management of state affairs. The analysis showed that some of the rights are significantly distorted in practice, some cannot be used due to the obstacles of the authorities, and some are not used by the citizens themselves due to the mentally determined social status of a "little person".

The next example. A group of psychologists led by Professor V. Rybalka in the process of conducting constant trainings (to increase the ability of the individual to act in modern civil society) came to the conclusion that "the weakness of civic education... and the manifestation of insufficient development, the actual absence of adult civil society" [7, p. 193-194].

Thus, from the very beginning of the declaration of independence, Ukraine had a large layer of people with mental negative consequences from the past. The active part of this stratum wanted to compensate for their low self-sufficiency through supremacy over other people due to being in power. The other part of this stratum (more decent, but less active) was infected with inertia to state affairs. And even realizing the ugliness of the electoral system, in which citizens silently went to

the ballot boxes, voted at random for those who were liked by the leaders of the parties or the current government, each time choosing the wrong one... And one more thing, there were no clear "white" filters for the admission of people capable of operating in high responsible positions to the elite.

"White" filters are implemented, initially using a system of special tests. Subsequently, the educational branch will join the definition and formation of qualities according to these criteria, diagnosing universal morality and analytical-cognitive activity from kindergartens (and from adolescence, children are instilled with curiosity about self-knowledge of their own "Self"). In the future, self-exploration of one's own "Self" may help to enhance the effectiveness of the "white" filter. For example, when an applicant who wants to take an elite position deliberately refuses it, realizing his non-compliance with these criteria.

The philosophy of human-centeredness can become an attractive unifying force and a real ideology for the development of post-war Ukraine (and the whole world) if we pay special attention to two factors.

The first factor is the deepening of the concept of "human-centrism", which today some stratum of unconscious people associate with the priority of human life over nature. Therefore, it is necessary to understand human-centeredness as "ecological human-centeredness" or simply "eco-human-centrism" as an organic positive unity of man with nature and even as its preserver.

The second factor is the transparent actions of the authorities in line with the ideology of human-centeredness. The inclusion of public organizations, not distorted by the authorities, as experts on the human-centeredness of any Laws, Presidential Decrees, Resolutions of Governments and even decisions of regional and local Councils can significantly change the situation and even "beat" corruption in a certain way.

We remind you that eco-human-centrism is the essence of democracy and the core of modern civilization, which still needs to be brought to a state of harmony. Therefore, adherence to the human-centered ideology can help Ukraine to embark on a systematic path to modern civilization, which, we repeat, needs harmonization.

It is difficult to overestimate the new role of education in the modernization of the state system of Ukraine in the context of the implementation of the ideology of human-centeredness. At first glance, the educational sector suffered much less (than the economy and public morality) from the helpless management of the state. For a long time, Ukraine had one of the greatest educated human potentials, until it began to quickly lose it due to the deterioration of the quality of life of people and the search for an opportunity for many of them to realize themselves abroad. This potential was based on the achievements of outstanding, talented domestic teachers, including innovators: L. Vygotsky, M. Drahomanov, A. Makarenko, V. Sukhomlynsky, V. Shatalov, and others.

Today, the educational sector is a set of educational institutions and management structures, starting with the Ministry of Education and Science. All of them function in a haphazard space without a clear vision of

their unifying strategic goals and final results. And this is in the presence of a large number of slogans in the conditions of economic managerial culture, the culture of administrative pressure (CAP) as a source of bureaucracy and incompetence of the managerial level.

The lack of measured final results of activity (FRA) of the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine does not allow the education system to be called a real "system". Because there is no system-forming core of its functioning as a certain integrity, all elements and parts of which would interact harmoniously with each other, complementing and strengthening each other.

It is the lack of clear FRAs that determines the managerial culture of administrative pressure (CAP), when the tops lead without being responsible for the negative consequences of their management. Ministers can be incompetent, dishonest, unpatriotic people without large-scale thinking, and bureaucracy can cover all links of educational activity. Bearing in mind that bureaucracy "entails" a great waste of time and energy in the entire galaxy of educators, many of whom (especially teachers) work on the verge of professional burn-out.

There is already a technology for "curing" the disease of unsystematic and bureaucracy. This is the culture of system management (CSM) according to the final results, which should gradually replace CAP, which is still operating in the educational sector. But the CSM is still unknown to the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, although there are already several publications on this subject [7; 8; 9].

The New Human-Centered Management Course (NHMC) is a system complex of four blocks, including a triad of interconnected anti-corruption levers, powerful technologies. These technologies have a human-centric orientation based on the culture of systemic management based on the final results.

The final results are the indices of the quality of life of citizens as components that characterize the level of happiness of people in five spheres of their life. Briefly about the four blocks, three of which are system technologies, we remind you below:

The first block contains targets which includes: the ideology of human-centeredness (eco-human-centrism); the mission, which is related to the construction of a society of happy people; strategic goals and final results of the activities of the power structures that orient the activities of the latter to improve the quality of life of citizens as components of happiness.

The second block is technological, related to the determination of the QLC indices in the process of a kind of local referendum at the national level called "Digital Viche".

The third block is technological too, which ensures the transition of power structures at all hierarchical levels to a culture of systemic management based on the final results, which is the level of quality of life of citizens (QLC).

The fourth block is technological, which opens up new opportunities for national education to become peacemaking through the conscious formation of the best human qualities through the use of qualimetric digitalization in the educational process.

What does The New Human-Centered Management Course (NHMC) propose in this context, helping Ukraine to embark on the path of civilizational development?

Since the movement towards a harmonious civilization follows the path of deepening human-centrism (eco-human-centrism), NHMC proposes to perform, first of all, through the humanization of relations between the government and people. In particular, using the annual target assessment of the resulting actions of the authorities (in a digital way), which are indices of the quality of life of citizens (QLC) as components of their happiness. These QLC indices are determined in the context of satisfying needs in all spheres of human life. The humanistic thesis becomes real: "The status of the government depends on how its people live."

In line with the deepening of human-centrism, in order to contribute as much as possible, for example, to the self-realization of each individual, and the formation of a managerial elite according to abilities, people need to know the truth about themselves. Therefore, NHMC offers a technology of qualimetric digitalization of the conscious formation of the best human qualities, which ensures the generation of interest in self-knowledge of one's own "Self" from adolescence. And much more.

Conclusions and suggestions. In Ukraine, which is rich in natural resources, there is one extremely important key problem, it is the problem of power. Therefore, it is necessary to start restoring order in the country, with the authorities, in particular, their responsibility to the people.

But Ukraine is a special country with a special corrupt government, where all known methods (including typical means of civil society) of influencing it to direct its actions to the well-being of the people do not work.

Ukraine has no experience in the formation of modern civil society, having in its history only some manifestations of its elements. This applies to the Viche in Kyiv (1068), and the Cossack Council, and the Magdeburg Law (from the XIV-XV centuries to as far as 1835), and the Zaporizhzhya Sich, etc. Two Maidans (2004 and 2014) aroused the consciousness of citizens, but they did little to improve the state system in terms of anti-corruption changes, because some corrupt officials replaced others.

If the existing "system of public administration" in Ukraine is really transformed into a system as a whole, in which all structures and specialists would work harmoniously for a single human-centered goal (helping each other), then it will be realistic to raise Ukraine to the level of modern civilization... Such a goal has al-

ready been defined: improving the quality of life of citizens as an organic component of their happiness. It is only necessary to learn how to measure this "increase" digitally, to make it a valid lever of system control, completely eliminating slogans.

This will be one of the managerial innovations of the NHMC in post-war Ukraine, which is gradually turning into an innovative social technology. Thus, the NHMC as a holistic outline of the social project of cardinal modernization of the state system of Ukraine is aimed at improving modern civilization in the course of its further humanization in a harmonious combination of the interests of a particular person and society, as well as humanity.

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